

Ewing's of the Wing

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ABSTRACT Ewing's sarcoma is the 2nd most common tumor in adolescents after osteosarcoma with a peak incidence between 10-20 years with a male preponderance (1.6:1). It arises from neuroectodermal crest cells and rarely involves the scapula. The treatment involves neo-adjuvant chemotherapy followed by surgical resection & radiotherapy. Radiological evaluation played a vital role in substantiating the diagnosis which was established by histopathological & immunohistochemistry correlation in this case of an 11 year old girl with pain & swelling over the right shoulder for 6 months.

KEYWORDS Ewing's sarcoma, Scapula, Imaging, Radiology, X-ray, CT, MRI, USG

Introduction

Ewing Sarcoma (ES) is a highly malignant small round cell tumour (rare) that primarily affects the skeletal system. In primary extraosseous ES of soft tissue underlying bone involvement is not found. James Ewing described it in 1921 as a tumour arising from undifferentiated osseous mesenchymal cells; recent studies have suggested neuroectodermal origin being derived from the primitive neural tissue. Four to 10% of all types of bone cancers, with long bones and pelvis being the most common sites. Second most common bone tumour of childhood and adolescence, with a male preponderance of 1.6:1. Rarely seen before the age of five and when the age of thirty years. The ES usually arises in the metaphysis or diaphysis of long bones of extremities. The lungs, bones and bone marrow are the most common sites of metastasis. [1] This report describes a case of an 11 year old girl and illuminates the importance of imaging and knowledge of the relevant aspects.

Case report

An 11-year-old female presented with a history of pain & rapidly growing swelling over the right shoulder girdle region with no relief on non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medication. Clinically, there was swelling over the right shoulder about 10x8cm in size

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

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Figure 3:

Figure 7:

Figure 4:

Figure 8:

Figure 5:

Figure 9:

Figure 6:

Figure 10:

Figure 11:

Figure 12:

Figure 13:

Figure 14:

(Figure1 - Clinical Image). The swelling was firm to hard in consistency. The overlying skin was normal.

General and systemic examinations were within normal limits. Hemogram, urea, creatinine, SGOT, SGPT Sr. Bilirubin (total / direct) were normal.

We have raised CRP measuring 3.7mg/L. Plain X-ray (Figure 2 - Right Shoulder): Soft tissue swelling over the right shoulder girdle with a lytic lesion involving the spine of the scapula. There is a widening of the acromioclavicular joint on the same side. USG (Figure 3&4- Grayscale and colour Doppler): Well-defined heterogenous mass lesion measuring about 9x7cm in the shoulder region with involvement of the muscles both dorsal & ventral to the shoulder. The lesion shows increased vascularity on Doppler. The underlying bony cortices appear irregular. CT (Figure 5&6- Bone and soft tissue window): Right scapula shows permeative lytic destruction with saucerization & hair-on-end appearance. It is sparing of the glenoid. Soft tissue involving the subscapularis, infraspinatus & subscapularis noted. MRI (Figure 7,8,9 - T1 Post contrast axial, coronal; STIR sagittal): A Large 10x9x7cm heterogeneously hyperintense lesion involving the entire scapula with early erosive/ destructive changes. The lesion involves the rotator cuff muscles- supraspinatus, infraspinatus & subscapularis. After imaging, Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology & core needle biopsy revealed a diffuse proliferation of monotonous cells having centrally placed large nuclei- small, round cell neoplasm suggesting Ewing's sarcoma / primitive neuroectodermal tumour (PNET- Figure 10 & 11- Cytology and Histopathology). Immunohistochemistry of the tumour cells was positive for CD 99 (Figure 12) and vimentin (Figure 13). The patient is on neo-adjuvant chemotherapy with a significant decrease in the size of the lesion after 3months (Figure 14 - Xray).

Discussion

The initial theory for the cell of origin of Ewing's sarcoma included endothelial and undifferentiated mesenchymal cells of the bone marrow. The advent of immunohistochemistry and cytogenetic evaluation suggested a neuroectodermal origin. [2] Ewing sarcoma commonly arises from bone and may also involve soft tissues at the time of the presentation. Rarely, may have an extraskeletal origin. Ewing sarcoma is a rapidly growing, round-cell, malignant tumour which can reach about 10 cm by the time of the diagnosis. [3] Typically occurs in children and adolescents between 10 and 20 years of age (95% between 4 and 25 years of age), and has a slight male predilection (M: F 1.5:1). [4,5] Most frequently, the sites involved are femur and tibia in the lower extremity, and upper limb humerus is involved commonly. In upper limb involvement of scapula is rare. The patient typically presents with pain and a quickly growing swelling followed by general symptoms like weight loss and fever in some cases. [6,7] Extraskeletal Ewing sarcoma is confirmed by the characteristic appearance on histology, immunohistochemistry and electron microscopy. Differential diagnoses include small, blue round cell tumours (SBRCTs) and other members of the Ewing family of tumours such as the primitive neuroectodermal tumour (PNET). [8] With the advent of cytogenetic evaluation demonstrating that Ewing sarcoma, PNET, and Askin tumour share a common karyotypic abnormality was possible. Approximately 90% of these lesions show translocation between the long arms of chromosomes 11 and 22 (t [11;22] [q24;q12]). [9,10] The management of Ewing's sarcoma includes neoadjuvant chemotherapy to decrease tumour mass followed by wide excision and then by chemo and radiation therapy for margin-

positive tumours after biopsy or for palliation from pain. The prognosis depends upon Stage of the disease, tumour size and anatomic location. [11] Although most cases of ES present as localized disease, overt metastases are capable of developing rapidly. A microscopic metastatic disease has been postulated to be present at the time of presentation. However, the spread is held in check by unidentified factors secreted by the primary tumour. When the primary tumour is removed or irradiated, the loss of the putative suppressive factors may allow the metastases to grow further. The use of chemotherapy in conjunction with surgery or irradiation therapy to treat presumed metastasis has considerably improved survival. [12]

Conclusion

The scapula may contain a variety of benign and malignant tumours, with similar lytic expansile appearances on radiological imaging. With the advancement of limb salvage procedures, it becomes imperative on the radiologist to identify the extent of a tumour accurately as it will dictate the further management of the patient.

Competing Interests

None

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None

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